

Supplementary Materials for Quantifying Barriers of Urban Mobility

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S1 COVID-19 data set

Six months of mobility data is used before the COVID-19 pandemic (between September 2019 and February 2020) to analyze the barrier effect in urban mobility. As a part of the epidemic prevention strategy, restrictions have been issued, which limited to the mobility.

To compare the barrier effect during the pandemic, another 6-month interval was selected from the available mobile positioning data. In Hungary, the second and third waves took place between the autumn of 2020 and the spring of 2021.

The strictest protocols were issued between 11 November 2020 and the late May 2021, including curfew in nighttime. To match the pandemic data set as close as possible to the pre-pandemic data set, the six months between November 2020 and April 2021 have been selected. Figure S1 shows the selected interval in comparison to the weekly number of deaths during the pandemic.

Figure S1: COVID-19 mortality in Hungary between January 2020 and December 2021. The selected interval is considered the second and third wave in Hungary. Data is from European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control [1].

S2 Stability of the community detection

To test the stability of the community detection, the Cramér's V was applied to the communities by resolution. Figure S2a shows the kernel density plots of the Cramér's V values by resolution, with the medians using white dotted lines. At low resolution the median V value is high, but strongly distributed. The median decreases until $\gamma = 6$, then it starts converging to 0.78, while the distribution gets narrower. Furthermore, the trend of the medians is analogous to the Symmetric Area Difference (SAD). Figure S2b show the correlations (Pearson's R) between the medians and the SAD by barrier type. There are strong positive correlations between the barrier types, except the river where the correlation is strong, but negative as the river behaves differently (Figure S6b in contrast to Figure 3).

Figure S2: Cramér's V in contrast to the resolution, showing median values with white dotted lines (a), and the correlation (Pearson's R) between the V median and the Symmetric Area Difference (b).

S3 Enclosures

A Python script was developed to obtain enclosed areas from OpenStreetMap (OSM) with different type of roads and other potential barriers, based on [2]. To select the roads that were considered as barriers, the classification system of OSM is used. The script can be parameterized which road types should be included. The road types are taken into consideration in three levels: (i) “primary” including OSM motorway and OSM primary types, (ii) “secondary” which extends the primary with the OSM primary type (Figure S3a), and (iii) every road (Figure S3b). At the third level, the concept is extended to every lower-order streets until the enclosures became blocks.

Note that trunks are omitted from the analysis in this study. Trunks and motorways are not significant within the administrative boundaries of Budapest. There are actually more trunks (27.2 km) than freeway (12.6 km) but freeways continue as primary roads whereas trunk are on the periphery (see Figure S3c) as mostly part of the M0 ring freeway.

Figure S3: Enclosure polygons generated from primary and secondary roads (a) and all roads (b), focusing to Budapest downtown. The ‘motorway’, ‘trunk’ and ‘primary’ road types within Budapest based on OSM data (c).

S4 Barrier types

The introduced method developed for line-based barriers types, or 'LineString' using Geographic Information System terminology. However, polygons, such as parks, might be also barriers. On the other hand, administrative barriers (districts and neighborhoods in the case of Budapest) are already polygons, though they divide the city into non-overlapping parts. Parks or industrial areas could also be used and their intersection with trips (as lines) can also be calculated. The only modification required is deciding whether a trip ending in the polygon (e.g., in a park) is considered a crossing, or not. This case does not apply to our current implementation as the river and wide, multilane roads are represented by lines, not polygons.

Figure S4 shows river Danube around Margaret Island. There are four trips in Figure S4, marked by letters a, b, c, and d. The blue line denotes the river midstream, which is stored as a 'MultiLineString', so treated as a single object algorithmically, resulting that all three trips considered as a single river crossing. Because Danube divides Budapest almost perfectly to two parts (note that district 21 is on a Csepel Island), this simplification is acceptable. However, in the case of other cities, or other analyses in Budapest, which, for example, focuses on the difference between the western and eastern branch around Margaret Island, this solution might be superseded.

Figure S4: River Danube around Margaret Island represented as a line by its midstream. Four trips are displayed (marked by letters a, b, c, and d). All of them are considered a single river crossing.

S5 Symmetric Area Difference Changes

Figure S5 shows the changes in symmetric area differences SAD by the resolution parameter (γ) of the Louvain community detection, for two selected districts. As stated in the main text, District 21 is on an island, which makes its boundaries very stable (Figure S5b). The symmetric area difference is minimal from resolution 2.5, and does not change later. In the case of District 15, it reaches the minimum at about $\gamma = 2.5$ (later during some runs), but it remains more or less stable only until $\gamma = 5.5$ to $\gamma = 6.5$, with some alternation between the community detection runs (Figure S5a). After that point, the community splits up, and the district loses its community-forming power.

Note that the midstream of river Danube is a natural district border between Buda- and Pest-side districts, but that also means that some water surface is part of the administrative area of the districts. As water surfaces are not classified to communities, they were removed from the area of the affected districts.

Figure S5: The changes in symmetric area differences by the resolution parameter of the Louvain community detection, in the cases of District 15 (a) and District 21 (b). The dotted line represents the area of the district as a reference.

S6 SAD of Railways and River Barriers

The main text introduces analysis on the community fit to urban barriers with Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) focusing on administrative barriers and the road infrastructure, before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

As for the railways, the fit is not so strong, and even worse before the pandemic. It has a minimum around $\gamma = 3$. Interestingly, during the pandemic the barriers effect regarding the railways are strengthened, which is the opposite effect as it was in respect of the roads and the administrative boundaries (Figure 3c and 3b of the main text).

Figure S6b show the SAD of the river enclosures. The river Danube divides Budapest to three parts (Figure S6c), excluding Margaret Island and Óbuda Island: Buda, Pest and Csepel (district 21). Although river midstream is the boundary between the Buda and Pest-side districts and definitely a strong natural barrier, the river Danube on its own does not create complete communities, except for District 21 (see Figure S5b). It is because Buda and Pest does not form a community, even at $\gamma = 1$ there are multiple communities both in Buda and Pest (Figure S6d).

Also note that the $\gamma = 1$ communities are roughly approximate the HCSO district group partitioning (Figure S8a), except that Csepel (District 21) is belongs to the South-Pest area and there is a larger green area at the eastern part, where the airport is located, that is in the same community as the Inner-Pest. There is not much residential are near the airport that can explain the size of that community part, but the airport has strong transportation ties to the city center.

Figure S6: The Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) regarding the railway lines (a) and the river Danube (b). In (a, b), the lines and shaded area represent the mean and the 95 % confidence interval of the SAD indicator as a measure of barrier fit of mobility clusters detected in ten iterations of the Louvain community detection algorithm. The river Danube divides Budapest into three main parts, illustrated in (c). Also, (d) shows a possible community partition at $\gamma = 1$ with the Louvain community detection.

S7 Workday and holiday differences

Using data from the pre-covid period, the differences between workdays and holidays are also analyzed. Figure S7 show the results. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) coefficients, analogous to the Figure 3a of the main text, show that the barrier effect is smaller for every barrier type on weekends and holidays than on workdays.

The Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) is illustrated in Figure S7b for workdays, and in Figure S7c for holidays. The BCR is higher in the weekends and holidays. In the case of BCR, the higher value means that less community crossings occurs, so people rather stay in their neighborhoods.

This aligns with the previous results. The workday–holiday differences were examined in contrast to mobility indicators in previous research c Note that this is also affected by the home location and the socioeconomic status, which are not evaluated in this study.

Figure S7: Barrier effect differences between workdays and holidays. Figure **a** shows the differences in the OLS coefficients between workdays (blue) and holidays (purple). Figure **b** (workdays) and **c** (holidays) depicts the difference in the Barrier Crossing Ratio.

S8 Barrier Crossing Ratio by home locations

Figure S8 shows the same as Figure 6 of the main text, but instead of highlighting the Budapest–agglomeration difference, it uses the different colors for every sector of the agglomeration and district groups of Budapest.

This representation can reveal additional details. In the case of the North Buda regarding the primary roads, the BCR behaves more like the agglomeration at small γ , but more like the rest of Budapest at higher resolution. The reason may be that the Buda-side districts are not divided by primary roads (see Figure S3c), so primary roads cannot form the communities in that area.

Figure S8: Barrier effect based on the users' home location groups compared to the communities of the original network. Figure **a** shows the seven district groups in Budapest and six sectors of the agglomeration, defined by HCSO. Figure **b** shows the changes of the crossing ratio regarding the type of the barrier.

The pre-pandemic network has been divided based on the home locations of the users to thirteen networks. However, the BCR was compared to the original network. Another approach is to determine communities for the new networks and compare the BCR to those communities. Figure S9 shows the BCR compared to the communities of each subnetwork, constructed for the seven district groups of Budapest and six sectors of the agglomeration (defined by HCSO).

The result also shows clear distinction between the Budapest and the agglomeration areas, except the river, where the western sectors of the agglomeration behave much closer to the city than to the eastern sectors. The city center is more complex and attracts more diverse people [3]. Crossing the river Danube seems more probable from the western agglomeration than from the eastern sectors. This assumption is supported by the visitation analysis, presented in Section S9. Furthermore, the order of the sectors remains practically the same for each barrier type. The BCR value of the eastern sectors are higher than the western sectors' for every γ value.

Figure S9: Barrier effect based on the users' home location groups compared to the communities of each subnetwork. Figure **b** shows the changes of the crossing ratio regarding the type of the barrier.

S8.1 Home-location-based Network Details

Figure S10c shows the density of the network. People living in Budapest create more dense networks than the people living in the agglomeration. Figure S10d shows the number of the detected inhabitant to give some context to the network density.

The coefficients of the gravity model are displayed in Figure S10b by barrier categories and home groups. North and South Buda stand closely together in almost every barrier category and differ from the Pest-side district groups. Among the agglomeration sectors there are also some clustering: Northern, Eastern and Southeastern sectors (East of the capital) significantly differ from the Southern, Western and Southwestern sectors.

Figure S10: Network details and the barrier effect based on the users' home location groups. The HCSO defines seven district groups in Budapest and six sectors of the agglomeration (a). From the Budapest mobility of the inhabitants of these areas, 13 networks was built and evaluated. Network density shown in c, the detected number of inhabitant in d, and the gravity model coefficients are displayed in b.

S9 Budapest Stops of Inhabitants Living in the Agglomeration

The commuting patterns from the agglomeration sectors to the district groups of Budapest are regularly analyzed by the census data and already studied using mobile network data [4]. Based on the mobile positioning data, utilized in this study, the visitation patterns of Budapest areas from the agglomeration is determined (Figure S11 and Table S1).

Figure S11 shows the distribution of visitations from the agglomeration sectors to the Budapest district groups, using the same colors as in Figure S9a. It is also in numerical format in Table S1, where the rows represent the district groups and the columns represent the agglomeration sectors.

As expected, most of the visit from the eastern sectors target the Pest-side (East of the river) and the city center, while the majority of the visitations from the western sectors trend to the Buda-side (West of the river) and also to the city center.

Figure S11: Visitation (stop) distribution within Budapest of the people living in the agglomeration.

Table S1: Stop distribution in the district groups (rows) of inhabitants living in the agglomeration sectors (column).

sector district group	Eastern	Northern	Northwestern	Southeastern	Southern	Western
Eastern Pest (inner)	0.2284	0.1031	0.0579	0.1697	0.0734	0.0609
Eastern Pest (outer)	0.2338	0.1086	0.0478	0.2399	0.0606	0.0395
Inner Pest	0.1978	0.2385	0.1637	0.1959	0.1954	0.1838
North Buda	0.0982	0.1484	0.4664	0.0780	0.1223	0.2606
North Pest	0.1434	0.3093	0.1494	0.0603	0.0634	0.0635
South Buda	0.0508	0.0419	0.0576	0.0616	0.2354	0.2917
South Pest	0.0475	0.0504	0.0571	0.1946	0.2495	0.1000

S10 Aggregated Barrier Crossing Ratio

The Section Barrier Crossing Ratio of the main text introduces the Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR), which measures the relationship between those mobility events that cross barriers and those that cross barriers and detected communities as well.

Figure S12a shows the change of the BCR changes according to the resolution (γ) during the pre-pandemic interval while Figure S12b shows the same during the pandemic. The two intervals are described in Section S1.

The BCR reaches roughly the same value at higher γ in both cases, however in the pre-pandemic data set that happens faster. This might be the result of the decreased mobility during the pandemic.

Figure S12: Aggregated Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) for the pre-pandemic (a) and the pandemic data sets (b).

S11 Complexity OLS tables

The Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) is regressed with an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression, using the formula (5) from the main text. The explanatory variables are the geographical distance of the user's home location from the city center and the complexity of amenity portfolio of the visited location as proposed by [3]. The BCR is explained separately by the barrier types of primary roads (Table S2), secondary roads (Table S3), districts (Table S4), neighborhoods (Table S5), rivers (Table S6), and railways (Table S7), and for increasing resolution (γ) values.

Table S2: Primary roads

dependent variable: $BCR^{\text{Primary roads}}$										
	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 2$	$\gamma = 3$	$\gamma = 4$	$\gamma = 5$	$\gamma = 6$	$\gamma = 7$	$\gamma = 8$	$\gamma = 9$	$\gamma = 10$
intercept	2.085*** (0.319)	0.669*** (0.184)	-0.009 (0.137)	-0.014 (0.131)	0.089 (0.120)	-0.639 (0.644)	-0.124 (0.202)	0.395*** (0.088)	0.311*** (0.115)	0.419*** (0.087)
distance (log10)	-0.117 (0.084)	0.180*** (0.048)	0.338*** (0.036)	0.329*** (0.035)	0.288*** (0.032)	0.489*** (0.170)	0.337*** (0.053)	0.188*** (0.023)	0.208*** (0.030)	0.177*** (0.023)
complexity	0.150*** (0.027)	-0.137*** (0.016)	-0.094*** (0.012)	-0.097*** (0.011)	-0.077*** (0.010)	-0.081 (0.054)	-0.086*** (0.017)	-0.092*** (0.007)	-0.076*** (0.010)	-0.089*** (0.007)
observations	15697	15957	16126	16263	16343	16418	16472	16500	16521	16549
R ²	0.003	0.007	0.013	0.014	0.012	0.001	0.006	0.018	0.009	0.017
adjusted R ²	0.002	0.007	0.013	0.014	0.012	0.001	0.006	0.018	0.009	0.017

Table S3: Secondary roads

dependent variable: $BCR^{\text{Secondary roads}}$										
	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 2$	$\gamma = 3$	$\gamma = 4$	$\gamma = 5$	$\gamma = 6$	$\gamma = 7$	$\gamma = 8$	$\gamma = 9$	$\gamma = 10$
intercept	2.358*** (0.237)	1.044*** (0.217)	0.093 (0.199)	-0.029 (0.428)	0.271* (0.143)	0.171 (0.125)	0.137 (0.131)	0.256*** (0.129)	0.300*** (0.102)	0.192* (0.105)
distance (log10)	-0.169*** (0.062)	0.128*** (0.057)	0.345*** (0.052)	0.367*** (0.113)	0.269*** (0.038)	0.287*** (0.033)	0.288*** (0.034)	0.252*** (0.034)	0.236*** (0.027)	0.261*** (0.028)
complexity	-0.087*** (0.020)	-0.224*** (0.018)	-0.142*** (0.017)	-0.188*** (0.036)	-0.150*** (0.012)	-0.156*** (0.010)	-0.143*** (0.011)	-0.156*** (0.011)	-0.151*** (0.009)	-0.143*** (0.009)
observations	15747	15951	16139	16248	16339	16404	16453	16473	16501	16525
R ²	0.001	0.012	0.010	0.003	0.017	0.024	0.020	0.021	0.031	0.029
adjusted R ²	0.001	0.011	0.010	0.003	0.017	0.024	0.020	0.021	0.031	0.028

Table S4: Districts

	dependent variable: $BCR^{Districts}$									
	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 2$	$\gamma = 3$	$\gamma = 4$	$\gamma = 5$	$\gamma = 6$	$\gamma = 7$	$\gamma = 8$	$\gamma = 9$	$\gamma = 10$
intercept	3.022*** (0.275)	1.132*** (0.205)	-0.097 (0.170)	0.092 (0.159)	0.191 (0.139)	0.052 (0.133)	-0.007 (0.130)	0.143 (0.114)	0.105 (0.115)	0.065 (0.109)
distance (log10)	-0.225*** (0.072)	0.191*** (0.054)	0.469*** (0.045)	0.395*** (0.042)	0.346*** (0.037)	0.374*** (0.035)	0.378*** (0.034)	0.328*** (0.030)	0.335*** (0.030)	0.339*** (0.029)
complexity	-0.113*** (0.023)	-0.335*** (0.017)	-0.201*** (0.014)	-0.242*** (0.013)	-0.209*** (0.012)	-0.220*** (0.011)	-0.217*** (0.011)	-0.218*** (0.009)	-0.220*** (0.010)	-0.215*** (0.009)
observations	15831	16035	16202	16321	16400	16467	16516	16538	16562	16585
R ²	0.002	0.029	0.026	0.034	0.033	0.041	0.042	0.050	0.050	0.055
adjusted R ²	0.002	0.028	0.026	0.034	0.033	0.040	0.042	0.050	0.050	0.054

Table S5: Neighborhoods

	dependent variable: $BCR^{Neighborhoods}$									
	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 2$	$\gamma = 3$	$\gamma = 4$	$\gamma = 5$	$\gamma = 6$	$\gamma = 7$	$\gamma = 8$	$\gamma = 9$	$\gamma = 10$
intercept	1.466*** (0.266)	0.404* (0.219)	-0.522*** (0.182)	-0.209 (0.179)	0.035 (0.161)	-0.071 (0.158)	-0.044 (0.138)	0.201* (0.115)	0.183 (0.118)	0.162 (0.114)
distance (log10)	0.150*** (0.070)	0.359*** (0.058)	0.566*** (0.048)	0.462*** (0.047)	0.376*** (0.042)	0.396*** (0.042)	0.376*** (0.036)	0.301*** (0.030)	0.303*** (0.031)	0.304*** (0.030)
complexity	-0.048*** (0.023)	-0.244*** (0.018)	-0.155*** (0.015)	-0.202*** (0.015)	-0.172*** (0.013)	-0.190*** (0.013)	-0.187*** (0.012)	-0.193*** (0.010)	-0.195*** (0.010)	-0.193*** (0.009)
observations	15831	16035	16202	16321	16400	16467	16516	16538	16562	16585
R ²	0.001	0.018	0.021	0.023	0.020	0.025	0.030	0.040	0.038	0.041
adjusted R ²	0.001	0.018	0.020	0.023	0.020	0.025	0.030	0.039	0.038	0.041

Table S6: River

	dependent variable: BCR^{River}									
	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 2$	$\gamma = 3$	$\gamma = 4$	$\gamma = 5$	$\gamma = 6$	$\gamma = 7$	$\gamma = 8$	$\gamma = 9$	$\gamma = 10$
intercept	-0.064 (0.106)	-0.328*** (0.078)	-0.344*** (0.101)	-0.397*** (0.061)	-0.404*** (0.063)	-0.381*** (0.061)	-0.375*** (0.064)	-0.334*** (0.061)	-0.328*** (0.063)	-0.329*** (0.065)
distance (log10)	0.242*** (0.028)	0.299*** (0.021)	0.299*** (0.027)	0.300*** (0.016)	0.300*** (0.017)	0.293*** (0.016)	0.291*** (0.017)	0.280*** (0.016)	0.278*** (0.017)	0.278*** (0.017)
complexity	0.102*** (0.009)	0.092*** (0.007)	0.117*** (0.009)	0.121*** (0.005)	0.127*** (0.005)	0.125*** (0.005)	0.126*** (0.005)	0.126*** (0.005)	0.122*** (0.005)	0.124*** (0.005)
observations	15788	15994	16102	16311	16390	16457	16506	16525	16548	16574
R ²	0.010	0.019	0.015	0.042	0.042	0.044	0.040	0.043	0.038	0.037
adjusted R ²	0.010	0.019	0.015	0.042	0.042	0.043	0.040	0.043	0.037	0.037

Table S7: Railways

	dependent variable: BCR^{Railways}									
	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 2$	$\gamma = 3$	$\gamma = 4$	$\gamma = 5$	$\gamma = 6$	$\gamma = 7$	$\gamma = 8$	$\gamma = 9$	$\gamma = 10$
intercept	0.004 (0.217)	-0.021 (0.183)	-0.548*** (0.187)	-0.450*** (0.151)	-0.081 (0.121)	-0.175 (0.137)	-0.157* (0.089)	0.345*** (0.076)	0.426*** (0.078)	0.326*** (0.070)
distance (log10)	0.404*** (0.057)	0.376*** (0.048)	0.499*** (0.049)	0.453*** (0.040)	0.334*** (0.032)	0.357*** (0.036)	0.341*** (0.023)	0.199*** (0.020)	0.175*** (0.020)	0.198*** (0.018)
complexity	-0.128*** (0.019)	-0.188*** (0.015)	-0.138*** (0.016)	-0.127*** (0.013)	-0.095*** (0.010)	-0.100*** (0.011)	-0.097*** (0.007)	-0.108*** (0.006)	-0.112*** (0.006)	-0.107*** (0.006)
observations	15697	15923	16117	16259	16347	16428	16465	16506	16536	16559
R ²	0.009	0.018	0.015	0.019	0.017	0.015	0.032	0.031	0.029	0.036
adjusted R ²	0.009	0.018	0.015	0.019	0.017	0.015	0.032	0.031	0.029	0.036

S12 YJMob100K

A metropolitan scale, longitudinal, and anonymized mobility trajectory data was released [5], which aims to be a benchmark dataset of human mobility [6]. The presented approach was applied to the ‘YJMob100K’ data set, which already contains trajectories in their raw form. The exact procedure that made it possible to use the ‘YJMob100K’ data for this study can be found in [7]. The difference is that the trajectories connect 500 meters by 500 meters grid cells, instead of blocks extracted from the road network. Figure S13b and S13c illustrate the results of the community detection procedure at resolution (γ) 1, 5, and 12 in contrast of the municipalities (solid line) and wards (dotted line) extracted from OpenStreetMap (OSM). The mobility clusters match the administrative boundaries, but a community often matches multiple municipalities. Interestingly, this effect does not apply to the road network (Figure S13d, S13e, S13f) as in the case of Budapest (Figure 1 of the main text). Note that the water surfaces are excluded from the municipality boundaries. However, activities occur there (e.g., people using ferries), which can be observed in the data, so some of those cells are associated with communities.

The Symmetric Area Difference (SAD) is calculated (Figure S13g) compared to the municipality boundaries (admin level 7 in OSM) and the wards of Nagoya (admin level 8 in OSM). In both cases, the SAD approximates the administrative boundaries as the resolution increases.

The individual Barrier Crossing Ratio (BCR) is also determined based on the ‘YJMob100K’ data. Similarly to the Budapest case, people with estimated home locations within Nagoya (18,699 individuals) are distinguished from the rest of the users. Just as in the case of Budapest, the two groups show different exposure to the barrier effect (Figure S13h and S13i), however, as opposed to Budapest the relation of the two trends are the opposite.

In this section, we demonstrated our approach on a different data set covering a much larger area from a different part of the world. The ‘YJMob100K’ data set follows 100,000 people in about a 100 km by 100 km area, while Budapest and its agglomeration is about 2540 km². The administrative area of Nagoya as a principal city is 326.45 km², which is about the 62% of Budapest (525.14 km²), however, Nagoya is the center of the Chūkyō metropolitan area with the area of 7072 km². In our study, we focused on mobility that took place within the administrative boundaries of Budapest, a smaller area but with more users. Due to the high number of differences not every result shows exactly the expected finding. Further study is required, involving data about more cities, to explore the barrier effect in more types of cities.

Figure S13: Louvain communities compared to administrative boundaries at resolution 1 (a), 5 (b), and 12 (c), and compared to the road network at resolution 1, 5, and 12 (d, e, and f respectively). The decreasing Symmetric Area Difference shows an improving fit of mobility clusters to the administrative boundaries (g). The individual Barrier Crossing Ratio shows that the barriers like municipality boundaries (h) and primary roads (i) affect people less if they have home locations in Nagoya compared to those who live in its agglomeration.

Abbreviations

BCR Barrier Crossing Ratio

GIS Geographic Information System

HCSO Hungarian Central Statistical Office

OLS Ordinary Least Squares

OSM OpenStreetMap

SAD Symmetric Area Difference

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